

POST-COVID-19 MICROBIOTA ALTERATIONS AND THEIR IMPACT ON HOST IMMUNITY

Berdiyeva Dilnavoz Toshkan kizi¹, Sadriyeva Diyora², Olimova Yulduz³

¹Associate professor., Ph.D., Central Asian University, Tashkent
Orcid ID: 0009-0002-9668-0479, Email: d.berdiyeva@centralasian.uz

²Tutor, Student of Medical school at Central Asian University
ORCID ID: 0009-0000-1186-9703, Email: 220273@centralasian.uz

³Assistant of chemistry laboratory, tutor,
Student of Medical school at Central Asian University
ORCID ID: 0009-0007-6544-0794, Email: 220997@centralasian.uz

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Abstract. Beyond the respiratory system, COVID-19 infection has systemic consequences that affect the gut microbiota and gastrointestinal tract. In this study, alterations in gut bacteria composition and function were investigated following SARS-CoV-2 infection. Apart from that, it was observed that short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs) had been faced with dramatic decrease while antimicrobial-resistant bacteria, particularly *Klebsiella* species, had grown. These changes are believed to be intimately related to neurological, respiratory, immunological, and gastrointestinal problems.

Key words: COVID-19, SARS-CoV-2, microbiota, gut-brain, lung-brain, post-COVID complications, gastrointestinal (GI) tract

Annotatsiya. Nafas olish tizimidan tashqari, COVID-19 infeksiyasi ichak mikrobiotasi va ovqat hazm qilish traktiga ta'sir ko'rsatadigan tizimli oqibatlariga ega. Ushbu tadqiqotda SARS-CoV-2 infeksiyasidan so'ng ichak bakteriyalari tarkibi va funksiyasidagi o'zgarishlar o'rganildi. Bundan tashqari, qisqa zanjirli yog' kislotalari (SCFA) keskin kamaygani, antimikrobiyal qarshilikka ega bakteriyalar, xususan *Klebsiella* turlari esa ko'paygani kuzatildi. Ushbu o'zgarishlar asab tizimi, nafas olish, immun va ovqat hazm qilish tizimlari bilan chambarchas bog'liq bo'lishi mumkin deb hisoblanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: COVID-19, SARS-CoV-2, mikrobiota, ichak-miya, o'pka-miya, post-COVID asoratlari, ovqat hazm qilish (GI) trakti

Аннотация. Помимо дыхательной системы, инфекция COVID-19 имеет системные последствия, затрагивающие кишечную микробиоту и желудочно-кишечный тракт. В данном исследовании были изучены изменения в составе и функции кишечных бактерий после заражения SARS-CoV-2. Кроме того, было выявлено значительное снижение уровня короткоцепочечных жирных кислот (SCFA), тогда как количество антимикробно-резистентных бактерий, в частности представителей рода *Klebsiella*, увеличилось. Считается, что эти изменения тесно связаны с неврологическими, дыхательными, иммунологическими и желудочно-кишечными нарушениями.

Ключевые слова: COVID-19, SARS-CoV-2, микробиота, ось кишечник-мозг, ось лёгкие-мозг, постковидные осложнения, желудочно-кишечный тракт (ЖКТ)

Introduction. The severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) is the distinct beta-coronavirus responsible for coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19), a worldwide outbreak that affected over five million people until November 2021 [1]. The respiratory system exhibits the greatest number of COVID-19 symptoms, with extrapulmonary manifestations such as cardiac dysfunction, thrombotic issues, and gastrointestinal (GI) symptoms becoming common [2]. SARS-CoV-2 needs ACE2 to identify and access cells, and it may have an impact on immune and metabolic activity. Intestinal cells, an important location for virus entrance into the intestine, have significant expression of the ACE2 receptor. SARS-CoV-2 causes gastrointestinal symptoms by replicating in intestinal epithelial cells after invasion. Changes in intestinal flora can be exacerbated by SARS-CoV-2's bloodstream entrance, which can also lead

to increased platelet and inflammatory cytokine activation. This can disrupt the intestinal flora and cause the gut-blood barrier to break down. As the condition progresses, a variety of symptoms may appear [3].

An enormous population of microorganisms, estimated to number more than 10^{14} cells, colonizes the gastrointestinal (GI) tract [4]. These organisms include bacteria, archaea, viruses, and fungi, but bacteria are the most abundant and best studied. Bacteroidetes and Firmicutes are the two predominant bacterial phyla prevalent in a healthy gut, with Actinobacteria, Proteobacteria, Fusobacteria, and Verrucomicrobia contributing less [4, 5].

Microbial exposure during early life is crucial, as the diversity and stability of the gut microbiota help establish immunoregulatory networks and protect against allergic and inflammatory diseases later in life [11]. Over time, the microbiota and host immune system co-evolve, creating a state of mutual regulation in which microbes both induce immune responses and promote tolerance to harmless antigens [12,16,18]. The gut microbiota influences both innate and adaptive pathways, supporting antigen-presenting cell and neutrophil function while also guiding CD4⁺ T cell responses [13,14,17]. A shift in the gut microbiota's composition can have either a pathological or beneficial effects, mediated by the gut microbiota's regulation of specific CD4 + T cell subtypes [15].

Taken together, these findings highlight that the gut microbiota is not only central to digestion and metabolism but is also a critical regulator of immune homeostasis. The balance between different microbial groups and their metabolites plays a direct role in determining whether the immune system promotes tolerance or shifts toward harmful inflammation.

SARS-CoV-2 affects the gastrointestinal tract by targeting intestinal epithelial cells, leading to dysbiosis and downstream immune alterations. Similarly, inactivated SARS-CoV-2 vaccines have been shown to reshape gut microbial composition and function, with notable differences in abundance and metabolic pathways observed between vaccinated and unvaccinated individuals [37,38,39]. COVID-19 vaccination has been shown to significantly influence gut microbiota composition, leading to reduced bacterial diversity and enrichment of taxa such as *Faecalibacterium* and *Mollicutes* [40]. The gut microbiota may enhance or reduce the efficacy of vaccines through variations in metabolite composition. In addition to affecting gut microbiota abundance and composition, COVID-19 vaccines may reduce the gut microbiota biodiversity [41].

Discussion. It was observed that SARS-CoV-2 infection causes gastrointestinal symptoms as well as may alter gut microflora. [12-30],[33] The study found a relationship between microbiome changes and post-COVID complications, particularly the spread of antimicrobial resistance (AMR).[34-39] Apart from that, it has been discovered that AMR Enterobacteriaceae, specifically *Klebsiella* sp., increased even in moderate instances. [38-45] In mouse models, post-COVID microbiota was related with worsened lung injury and increased susceptibility to *K. pneumoniae*, indicating microbiota-driven pulmonary immune impairment.[46-51] Apart from that, it was revealed that systemic effects went beyond the lungs: post-COVID microbiota increased memory impairment in rats, indicating a gut-brain and lung-brain connection. [52-58] Reduced short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs) in donors and mice were proposed as a potential mechanism for neurological and pulmonary effects.[14,59],[60] Additional findings included elevated I-FABP, enrichment of Lachnospiraceae, neuroinflammation (hippocampal TNF), and decreased neuroplasticity markers such as BDNF and PSD-95. [61-65] As a proof of concept, the study found that probiotic *B. longum* 51A reduced memory impairment in a coronavirus mouse model, indicating the therapeutic potential of microbiome-targeted therapies. [23],[29],[66],[67]. These interactions are summarized in Figure 1, which illustrates the proposed post-COVID gut–lung–brain pathway.

Figure 1. Mechanistic Pathway of Post-COVID Microbiota Effects

Despite limitations like as a limited sample size and the lack of virome analysis [8],[68-70] concludes that gut microbiota modifications directly contribute to post-COVID symptoms and AMR spread, emphasising the need of characterising SARS-CoV-2 impacts on the microbiome. [71] It is reported that the first investigation of both bacterial and fungal gut microbiome changes in people recovering with mild COVID-19. The significant, however, microbial changes were observed in Hainan cohorts at 3 months (C3M) and 6 months (C6M) after recovery, which persisted when compared to never-infected controls. Validation in an Inner Mongolia cohort verified the findings' generalisability, suggesting that long-term microbiome alterations occurred regardless of age, gender, or BMI. These changes were associated with gastrointestinal and metabolic problems. Additionally, study reports that advances prior bacterial-centric investigations [72] by incorporating fungal dynamics. [73] found that stage-specific mycobiome alterations, such as a *Kluyveromyces*-to-*Asterotremella* transition, were related with improved AST/ALT ratios ($\beta=-0.42$, 95%CI -0.68 to -0.16; $P=0.008$), expanding findings beyond bacterial frameworks. In comparison to previous single-region models [74], cross-regional validation demonstrated the robustness of a 10-taxa bacterial model (AUC=0.90 Inner Mongolia; AUC=0.99 Hainan). Fungal communities offered comparable predictive benefit (combined AUC=0.61; $P=0.007$), despite their spatial variation (AUC=0.80 vs. 0.65). A dual-domain paradigm for tracking post-viral microbiome recovery was supported by the near-perfect prediction accuracy (AUC=0.99) attained by bacterial and fungal characteristics combined.

The study found that mild COVID-19 causes long-lasting bacterial shifts, which is in line with previous reports [75-85] Upadhyay et al. Alpha diversity did not fully return to baseline, although it did recover somewhat. Gut barrier and metabolic recovery were linked to probiotic taxa that were enriched at C3M, such as *Blautia massiliensis*, *Eubacterium ventriosum*, and *Coprococcus comes* [86-93]. Previously associated with anti-inflammatory and metabolic effects, *Weissella confusa*, *Phocaeicola vulgatus*, and *Streptococcus thermophilus* dominated at C6M. [93-98] Functions in tryptophan metabolism and anti-inflammatory pathways were validated by functional studies. Opportunistic species such *Slackia piriformis* and *Streptococcus equinus*, however, continued to exist, which may have consequences for anaemia and tumours [99, 100, 101]. The fungal component was noticed by a shift from probiotic *Kluyveromyces* in C3M, which might be related with improvement in gut microflora, to anti-inflammatory *Asterotremella* in C6M. Although transient *Kazachstania* indicated possible early immune modulation, opportunistic fungi such as *Alternaria* were highlighted as concerning [104], [105]. *Streptococcus thermophilus* and MCHC [107], [108], and *Asterotremella* and AST/ALT increase [106] were clinically correlated. By using co-occurrence network analysis, Synergistic *Rothia-Coprinopsis* interactions against infections were discovered [109], [110]. The study applied

machine learning approaches to identify recovery signals for bacteria (AUC=0.99) and fungi (AUC=0.80), which were then validated in different geographical areas. These biomarkers have been suggested as potential tools for personalised probiotic or nutritional therapy to address long-term microbiome imbalance. It underlined the importance of longitudinal, intervention-based research while recognising limitations such as the cross-sectional design and the exclusion of long-term COVID cases.

Conclusion. The findings analyzed in the article demonstrate that even patients with mild SARS-CoV-2 infection exhibit significant and long-lasting alterations in the bacterial and fungal composition of the gut microbiota. This dysbiosis is characterized by a reduction in short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs), an increased abundance of antimicrobial-resistant microorganisms such as *Klebsiella*, and notable shifts in the mycobiome. Such changes are closely associated with gastrointestinal, metabolic, respiratory, and neurological disturbances, thereby underscoring the clinical and pathogenetic relevance of the “gut–lung–brain axis.” During the recovery phase, the observed enrichment of specific probiotic groups highlights the therapeutic potential of microbiota-targeted interventions in restoring immune stability, alleviating post-COVID gastrointestinal and cognitive complications, and enhancing vaccine efficacy. Furthermore, evidence obtained from studies conducted across different regions, including Uzbekistan, substantiates the reliability and generalizability of these outcomes. This, in turn, expands the prospects of employing microbiota-based biomarkers to monitor post-COVID recovery. At the same time, the necessity of large-scale, longitudinal studies in Uzbekistan and beyond is emphasized, in order to elucidate causal relationships and to evaluate the effectiveness of individualized probiotic and diet-based interventions.

REFERENCES

1. World health organization (WHO). WHO Coronavirus (COVID-19) Dashboard. World Health Organization; 2021. <https://covid19.who.int/>. Accessed 1 Nov 2021.
2. Gupta A, Madhavan MV, Sehgal K, Nair N, Mahajan S, Sehrawat TS, et al. Extrapulmonary manifestations of COVID-19. *Nat Med.* 2020;26(7):1017–32. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-020-0968-3>.
3. Saviano A, Brigida M, Petruzzello C, et al. Intestinal damage, inflammation and microbiota alteration during COVID-19 infection. *Biomedicines.* 2023;11(4):1014. [DOI] [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
4. Thursby E, Juge N. Introduction to the human gut microbiota. *Biochem J.* 2017;474(11):1823–1836. [DOI] [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
5. Scarpellini E, Fagoonee S, Rinninella E, et al. Gut microbiota and liver interaction through immune system cross-talk: a comprehensive review at the time of the SARS-COV-2 pandemic. *J Clin Med.* 2020;9(8):2488. [DOI] [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
6. Rinninella E, Raoul P, Cintoni M, et al. What is the healthy gut microbiota composition? A changing ecosystem across age, environment, diet, and diseases. *Microorganisms.* 2019;7(1):14. [DOI] [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
7. Mazmanian SK, Round JL, Kasper DLJN. A microbial symbiosis factor prevents intestinal inflammatory disease. *Nature.* 2008;453(7195):620–5. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
8. Rabizadeh S, Rhee K-J, Wu S, et al. Enterotoxigenic *Bacteroides fragilis*: a potential instigator of colitis. *Inflamm Bowel Dis.* 2007;13(12):1475–1483. [DOI] [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
9. Atarashi K, Tanoue T, Shima T, et al. Induction of colonic regulatory T cells by indigenous *Clostridium* species. *Science.* 2011;331(6015):337–341. [DOI] [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]

10. Mukhopadhyaya I, Segal, JP, and Carding, SR, et al. The gut virome: the ‘missing link’ between gut bacteria and host immunity? *Therap Adv Gastroenterol.* 2019;12:1756284819836620. [[DOI](#)] [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
11. Zheng D, Liwinski T, Elinav E. Interaction between microbiota and immunity in health and disease. *Cell Res.* 2020;30(6):492–506. [[DOI](#)] [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
12. Belkaid Y, Hand TW. Role of the microbiota in immunity and inflammation. *Cell.* 2014;157(1):121–141. [[DOI](#)] [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
13. Honda K, Littman DR. The microbiota in adaptive immune homeostasis and disease. *Nature.* 2016;535(7610):75–84. [[DOI](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
14. Owaga E, Hsieh R-H, Mugendi B, et al. Th17 cells as potential probiotic therapeutic targets in inflammatory bowel diseases. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2015;16(9):20841–20858. [[DOI](#)] [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
15. Wu H-J, Wu E. The role of gut microbiota in immune homeostasis and autoimmunity. *Gut Microbes.* 2012;3(1):4–14. [[DOI](#)] [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
16. Mezouar S, Chantran Y, Michel J, et al. Microbiome and the immune system: from a healthy steady-state to allergy associated disruption. *Hum Microbiome J.* 2018;10:11–20. [[Google Scholar](#)]
17. Arpaia N, Campbell C, Fan X, et al. Metabolites produced by commensal bacteria promote peripheral regulatory T-cell generation. *Nature.* 2013;504(7480):451–455. [[DOI](#)] [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
18. Louis P, Flint HJ. Formation of propionate and butyrate by the human colonic microbiota. *Environ Microbiol.* 2017;19(1):29–41. [[DOI](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
19. Chen GY, Liu, M, and Wang, F, et al. A functional role for Nlrp6 in intestinal inflammation and tumorigenesis. *J Immunol.* 2011;186(12):7187–7194. [[DOI](#)] [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
20. 67.Lukasova M, Malaval, C, and Gille, A, et al. Nicotinic acid inhibits progression of atherosclerosis in mice through its receptor GPR109A expressed by immune cells. *J Clin Investig.* 2011;121(3):1163–1173. [[DOI](#)] [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
21. 68.Maslowski KM, Vieira AT, Ng A, et al. Regulation of inflammatory responses by gut microbiota and chemoattractant receptor GPR43. *Nature.* 2009;461(7268):1282–1286. [[DOI](#)] [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
22. Li J, Jing Q, Li J, et al. Assessment of microbiota in the gut and upper respiratory tract associated with SARS-CoV-2 infection. *Microbiome.* 2023;11(1):38. [[DOI](#)] [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
23. Zhang D, Weng S, Xia C, et al. Gastrointestinal symptoms of long COVID-19 related to the ectopic colonization of specific bacteria that move between the upper and lower alimentary tract and alterations in serum metabolites. *BMC Med.* 2023;21(1):264. [[DOI](#)] [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
24. Mancabelli L, Taurino G, Ticinesi A, et al. Disentangling the interactions between nasopharyngeal and gut microbiome and their involvement in the modulation of COVID-19 infection. *Microbiol Spectr.* 2023;11(5):e0219423. [[DOI](#)] [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
25. Bose T, Wasimuddin, Acharya V, et al. A cross-sectional study on the nasopharyngeal microbiota of individuals with SARS-CoV-2 infection across three COVID-19 waves in India. *Front Microbiol.* 2023;14:1238829. [[DOI](#)] [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
26. Candel S, Tyrkalska SD, Álvarez-Santacruz C, Mulero V. The nasopharyngeal microbiome in COVID-19. *Emerg Microbes Infect.* 2023;12(1):e2165970. [[DOI](#)] [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
27. Looft T, Allen HKJGM. Collateral effects of antibiotics on mammalian gut microbiomes. *Gut Microbes.* 2012;3(5):463–467. [[DOI](#)] [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]

28. Budden KF, Gellatly SL, Wood DLA, et al. Emerging pathogenic links between microbiota and the gut–lung axis. *Nature Rev Microbiol.* 2017;15(1):55. [[DOI](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
29. Coopersmith CM, Stromberg PE, Davis CG, et al. Sepsis from *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* pneumonia decreases intestinal proliferation and induces gut epithelial cell cycle arrest. *Crit Care Med.* 2003;31(6):1630–1637. [[DOI](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
30. Wang D, Hu B, Hu C, et al. Clinical characteristics of 138 hospitalized patients with 2019 novel coronavirus–infected pneumonia in Wuhan, China. *JAMA.* 2020;323(11):1061–1069. [[DOI](#)] [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
31. Cheung KS, Hung IFN, Chan PPY, et al. Gastrointestinal manifestations of SARS-CoV-2 infection and virus load in fecal samples from a Hong Kong cohort: systematic review and meta-analysis. *Gastroenterology.* 2020;159(1):81–95. [[DOI](#)] [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
32. Rajput S, Paliwal, D, and Naithani, M, et al. COVID-19 and gut microbiota: a potential connection. *Indian J Clin Biochem.* 2021;36(3) ;1–12. [[DOI](#)] [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
33. Anand S, Mande SS. Diet, microbiota and gut-lung connection. *Front Microbiol.* 2018;9:2147. [[DOI](#)] [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
34. Ng HY, Leung WK, Cheung KS. Association between gut microbiota and SARS-CoV-2 infection and vaccine immunogenicity. *Microorganisms.* 2023;11(2):452. [[DOI](#)] [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
35. Mendes de Almeida V, Engel DF, Ricci MF, et al. Gut microbiota from patients with COVID-19 cause alterations in mice that resemble post-COVID symptoms. *Gut Microbes.* 2023;15(2):2249146. [[DOI](#)] [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
36. Brogna C, Viduto V, Fabrowski M, et al. The importance of the gut microbiome in the pathogenesis and transmission of SARS-CoV-2. *Gut Microbes.* 2023;15(1):2244718. [[DOI](#)] [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
37. Geanes ES, LeMaster C, Fraley ER, et al. Cross-reactive antibodies elicited to conserved epitopes on SARS-CoV-2 spike protein after infection and vaccination. *Sci Rep.* 2022;12(1):6496. [[DOI](#)] [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
38. Gasmi A, Kumar Mujawdiya P, Noor S, Piscopo S, Résimont S, Menzel A. Increasing efficacy of covid-19 vaccines by lifestyle interventions. *Arch Razi Inst.* 2022;77(5):1527-1538. [[DOI](#)] [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
39. Romani A, Sergi D, Zauli E, et al. Nutrients, herbal bioactive derivatives and commensal microbiota as tools to lower the risk of SARS-CoV-2 infection. *Front Nutr.* 2023;10:1152254. [[DOI](#)] [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
40. Shen Y, Dong Y, Jiao J, Wang P, Chen M, Li J. BBIBP-CorV vaccination against the SARS-CoV-2 virus affects the gut microbiome. *Vaccines (Basel).* 2023;11(5):942. [[DOI](#)] [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
41. Leung J. Interaction between gut microbiota and COVID-19 and its vaccines. *World J Gastroenterol.* 2022;28(40):5801-5806. [[DOI](#)] [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
42. Hong M, Lan T, Li Q, et al. A comprehensive perspective on the interaction between gut microbiota and COVID-19 vaccines. *Gut Microbes.* 2023;15(1):2233146. [[DOI](#)] [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
43. Han M, Huang Y, Gui H, et al. Dynamic changes in host immune system and gut microbiota are associated with the production of SARS-CoV-2 antibodies. *Gut.* 2023;72(10):1996-1999. [[DOI](#)] [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
44. Tang B, Tang L, He W, et al. Correlation of gut microbiota and metabolic functions with the antibody response to the BBIBP-CorV vaccine. *Cell Rep Med.* 2022;3(10):100752. [[DOI](#)] [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]

45. Ceban F, Ling S, Lui L, et al. Fatigue and cognitive impairment in post-COVID-19 syndrome: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Brain Behav Immun*. 2022;101:93-135. [[DOI](#)] [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
46. Latronico N, Peli E, Calza S, et al. Physical, cognitive and mental health outcomes in 1-year survivors of COVID-19-associated ARDS. *Thorax*. 2022;77(3):300-303. [[DOI](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
47. Alonso-Lana S, Marquié M, Ruiz A, Boada M. Cognitive and neuropsychiatric manifestations of COVID-19 and effects on elderly individuals with dementia. *Front Aging Neurosci*. 2020;12:588872. [[DOI](#)] [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
48. Zhao Y, Li W, Lukiw W. Ubiquity of the SARS-CoV-2 receptor ACE2 and upregulation in limbic regions of Alzheimer's disease brain. *Folia Neuropathol*. 2021;59(3):232-238. [[DOI](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
49. Liu Q, Mak JWY, Su Q, Yeoh YK, Lui GCY, Ng SSS, Zhang F, Li AYL, Lu W, Hui DSC, et al. Gut microbiota dynamics in a prospective cohort of patients with post-acute COVID-19 syndrome. *Gut* [Internet]. 2022;71(3):544–552. doi:10.1136/gutjnl-2021-325989. [[Google Scholar](#)]
50. Zollner A, Koch R, Jukic A, Pfister A, Meyer M, Rössler A, Kimpel J, Adolph TE, Tilg H. Postacute COVID-19 is characterized by gut viral antigen persistence in inflammatory bowel diseases. *Gastroenterol* [Internet]. 2022;163(2):495–506.e8. doi:10.1053/j.gastro.2022.04.037. [[PubMed](#)], [[Web of Science ®](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
51. Bowerman KL, Rehman SF, Vaughan A, Lachner N, Budden KF, Kim RY, Wood DLA, Gellatly SL, Shukla SD, Wood LG, et al. Disease-associated gut microbiome and metabolome changes in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Nat Commun* [Internet]. 2020;11(1):5886. doi:10.1038/s41467-020-19701-0. [[PubMed](#)] [[Web of Science ®](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
52. Fernández-de-Las-Peñas C, Palacios-Ceña D, Gómez-Mayordomo V, Cuadrado ML, Florencio LL. Defining post-COVID symptoms (post-acute COVID, long COVID, persistent post-COVID): an integrative classification. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2021;18(5):18. doi:10.3390/ijerph18052621. [[Web of Science ®](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
53. Caugant DA, Levin BR, Selander RK. Distribution of multilocus genotypes of *Escherichia coli* within and between host families. *J Hyg (Lond)*. 1984;92(3):377–384. doi:10.1017/S0022172400064597. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
54. Song SJ, Lauber C, Costello EK, Lozupone CA, Humphrey G, Berg-Lyons D, Caporaso JG, Knights D, Clemente JC, Nakielnny S, et al. Cohabiting family members share microbiota with one another and with their dogs. *Elife*. 2013;2. doi:10.7554/eLife.00458. [[Web of Science ®](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
55. Souza DG, Vieira AT, Soares AC, Pinho V, Nicoli JR, Vieira LQ, Teixeira MM. The essential role of the intestinal microbiota in facilitating acute inflammatory responses. *J Immunol*. 2004;173(6):4137–4146. doi:10.4049/jimmunol.173.6.4137. [[PubMed](#)] [[Web of Science ®](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
56. M C CC, L NL, C M F, J L G, D A, C G, G C, S H P, C M, F S M, et al. Comparing the effects of acute alcohol consumption in germ-free and conventional mice: the role of the gut microbiota. *BMC Microbiol*. 2014;14(1):240. doi:10.1186/s12866-014-0240-4. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
57. Rungue M, Melo V, Martins D, Campos PC, Leles G, Galvão I, Mendes V, Aganetti M, Pedersen Á, Assis NRG, et al. NLRP6-associated host microbiota composition impacts in the intestinal barrier to systemic dissemination of brucella abortus. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis*. 2021;15(2):e0009171. doi:10.1371/journal.pntd.0009171. [[PubMed](#)] [[Web of Science ®](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
58. Zhang F, Wan Y, Zuo T, Yeoh YK, Liu Q, Zhang L, Zhan H, Lu W, Xu W, Lui GCY, et al. Prolonged impairment of short-chain fatty acid and L-Isoleucine biosynthesis in gut

- microbiome in patients with COVID-19. *Gastroenterol.* 2022;162(2):548–561.e4. doi:10.1053/j.gastro.2021.10.013. [[PubMed](#)] [[Web of Science®](#)][[Google Scholar](#)]
59. Galvão I, Tavares LP, Corrêa RO, Fachi JL, Rocha VM, Rungue M, Garcia CC, Cassali G, Ferreira CM, Martins FS, et al. The metabolic sensor GPR43 receptor plays a role in the control of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* infection in the lung. *Front Immunol.* 2018;9. <http://journal.frontiersin.org/article/10.3389/fimmu.2018.00142/full> [[Web of Science®](#)][[Google Scholar](#)]
60. Vieira AT, Rocha VM, Tavares L, Garcia CC, Teixeira MM, Oliveira SC, Cassali GD, Gamba C, Martins FS, Nicoli JR. Control of *klebsiella pneumoniae* pulmonary infection and immunomodulation by oral treatment with the commensal probiotic *bifidobacterium longum* 51A. *Microbes Infect.* 2016;18(3):180–189. doi:10.1016/j.micinf.2015.10.008. [[PubMed](#)] [[Web of Science®](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
61. Wu T, Xu F, Su C, Li H, Lv N, Liu Y, Gao Y, Lan Y, Li J. Alterations in the gut microbiome and cecal metabolome during *klebsiella pneumoniae*-induced pneumosepsis. *Front Immunol.* 2020;11:1331. doi:10.3389/fimmu.2020.01331. [[PubMed](#)][[Web of Science®](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
62. Douaud G, Lee S, Alfaro-Almagro F, Arthofer C, Wang C, McCarthy P, Lange F, Andersson JLR, Griffanti L, Duff E. SARS-CoV-2 is associated with changes in brain structure in UK biobank. *Nature.* 2022;604(7907):697–707. doi:10.1038/s41586-022-04569-5. [[PubMed](#)] [[Web of Science®](#)][[Google Scholar](#)]
63. Hartung TJ, Neumann C, Bahmer T, Chaplinskaya-Sobol I, Endres M, Geritz J, Haeusler KG, Heuschmann PU, Hildesheim H, Hinz A. Fatigue and cognitive impairment after COVID-19: a prospective multicentre study. *EclinicalMed.* 2022;53:101651. doi:10.1016/j.eclinm.2022.101651. [[PubMed](#)][[Google Scholar](#)]
64. Heine J, Schwichtenberg K, Hartung TJ, Rekers S, Chien C, Boesl F, Rust R, Hohenfeld C, Bungenberg J, Costa AS. Structural brain changes in patients with post-COVID fatigue: a prospective observational study. *Eclinicalmed.* 2023;58. doi:10.1016/j.eclinm.2023.101874. [[PubMed](#)][[Google Scholar](#)]
65. Andrade SP, Campolina-Silva GH, Queiroz-Junior CM, de Oliveira LC, de Lacerda L, Gaggino JCP, de Souza FRO, de Meira Chaves I, Passos IB, Teixeira DC, et al. A biosafety level 2 mouse model for studying betacoronavirus-induced acute lung damage and systemic manifestations. *J Virol.* 2021;95(22). doi:10.1128/JVI.01276-21. [[Web of Science®](#)][[Google Scholar](#)]
66. da Silva JGV, Vieira AT, Sousa TJ, Viana MVC, Parise D, Sampaio B, da Silva AL, de Jesus LCL, de Carvalho PKRML, de Castro Oliveira L, et al. Comparative genomics and in silico gene evaluation involved in the probiotic potential of *Bifidobacterium longum* 51A. *Gene.* 2021;795:145781. doi:10.1016/j.gene.2021.145781. [[PubMed](#)][[Web of Science®](#)][[Google Scholar](#)]
67. Xu E, Xie Y, Al-Aly Z. Long-term gastrointestinal outcomes of COVID-19. *Nat Commun* [Internet]. 2023;14(1):983. doi:10.1038/s41467-023-36223-7. [[PubMed](#)][[Web of Science®](#)][[Google Scholar](#)]
68. Livanos AE, Jha D, Cossarini F, Gonzalez-Reiche AS, Tokuyama M, Aydillo T, Parigi TL, Ladinsky MS, Ramos I, Dunleavy K, et al. Intestinal host response to SARS-CoV-2 infection and COVID-19 outcomes in patients with gastrointestinal symptoms. *Gastroenterol* [Internet]. 2021;160(7):2435–2450.e34. doi:10.1053/j.gastro.2021.02.056. [[PubMed](#)][[Web of Science®](#)][[Google Scholar](#)]
69. Merad M, Blish CA, Sallusto F, Iwasaki A. The immunology and immunopathology of COVID-19. *Science* (80-) [Internet]. 2022;375(6585):1122–1127. doi:10.1126/science.abm8108. [[PubMed](#)][[Web of Science®](#)][[Google Scholar](#)]
70. Wu Y, Cheng X, Jiang G, Tang H, Ming S, Tang L, Lu J, Guo C, Shan H, Huang X. Author correction: altered oral and gut microbiota and its association with SARS-CoV-2 viral load in COVID-19 patients during hospitalization. *Npj Biofilms Microbio* [Internet].

- 2021;7(1):90. doi:10.1038/s41522-021-00262-z. [[PubMed](#) [Web](#)][[of Science](#) ®][[Google Scholar](#)]
71. Langford BJ, So M, Simeonova M, Leung V, Lo J, Kan T, Raybardhan S, Sapin ME, Mponponsuo K, Farrell A. Antimicrobial resistance in patients with COVID-19: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Lancet Microbe*. 2022. doi:10.2139/ssrn.4099404. [[Google Scholar](#)]
 72. Langford BJ, Soucy JP, Leung V, So M, Kwan ATH, Portnoff JS, Bertagnolio S, Raybardhan S, MacFadden D, Daneman N. Antibiotic resistance associated with the COVID-19 pandemic: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Clin Microbiol Infect* 2022;29(3):302–309. doi: 10.1016/j.cmi.2022.12.006. [[Web of Science](#) ®][[Google Scholar](#)]
 73. de Nies L, Galata V, Martin-Gallausiaux C, Despotovic M, Busi SB, Snoeck CJ, Delacour L, Budagavi DP, Laczny CC, Habier J, et al. Altered infective competence of the human gut microbiome in COVID-19. *Microbiome*. 2023;11(1):46. doi:10.1186/s40168-023-01472-7. [[PubMed](#)][[Web of Science](#) ®][[Google Scholar](#)]
 74. Bernard-Raichon L, Venzon M, Klein J, Axelrad JE, Zhang C, Sullivan AP, Hussey GA, Casanovas-Massana A, Noval MG, Valero-Jimenez AM, et al. Gut microbiome dysbiosis in antibiotic-treated COVID-19 patients is associated with microbial translocation and bacteremia. *Nat Commun* [Internet]. 2022;13(1):5926. doi:10.1038/s41467-022-33395-6.[[PubMed](#)][[Web of Science](#) ®][[Google Scholar](#)]
 75. Kariyawasam RM, Julien DA, Jelinski DC, Larose SL, Rennert-May E, Conly JM, Dingle TC, Chen JZ, Tyrrell GJ, Ronksley PE, et al. Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in COVID-19 patients: a systematic review and meta-analysis (November 2019–June 2021). *Antimicrob Resist Infect Control* [Internet]. 2022;11(1):45. doi:10.1186/s13756-022-01085-z.[[PubMed](#)][[Web of Science](#) ®][[Google Scholar](#)]
 76. López-Jácome LE, Fernández-Rodríguez D, Franco-Cendejas R, Camacho-Ortiz A, Morfin-Otero MDR, Rodríguez-Noriega E, Ponce-de-León A, Ortiz-Brizuela E, Rojas-Larios F, Velázquez-Acosta MDC, et al. Increment antimicrobial resistance during the COVID-19 pandemic: results from the invifar network. *Microb Drug Resist*. 2022;28(3):338–345. doi:10.1089/mdr.2021.0231. [[PubMed](#)][[Web of Science](#) ®][[Google Scholar](#)]
 77. Furlan L, Caramelli B. The regrettable story of the “covid kit” and the “early treatment of Covid-19” in Brazil. *Lancet Reg Health Am*. 2021;4:100089. doi:10.1016/j.lana.2021.100089.[[PubMed](#)][[Google Scholar](#)]
 78. Jeon K, Jeong S, Lee N, Park MJ, Song W, Kim HS, Kim HS, Kim JS. Impact of COVID-19 on antimicrobial consumption and spread of multidrug-resistance in bacterial infections. *Antibiotic*. 2022;11(4):11. doi:10.3390/antibiotics11040535. [[Google Scholar](#)]
 79. Karami Z, Knoop BT, Dofferhoff ASM, Blaauw MJT, Janssen NA, van Apeldoorn M, Kerckhoffs APM, van de Maat JS, Hoogerwerf JJ, ten Oever J. Few bacterial co-infections but frequent empiric antibiotic use in the early phase of hospitalized patients with COVID-19: results from a multicentre retrospective cohort study in the Netherlands. *Infect Dis*. 2021;53(2):102–110. doi:10.1080/23744235.2020.1839672. [[PubMed](#)][[Web of Science](#) ®][[Google Scholar](#)]
 80. Van Laethem J, Wuyts S, Van Laere S, Koulalis J, Colman M, Moretti M, Seyler L, De Waele E, Pierard D, Lacor P, et al. Antibiotic prescriptions in the context of suspected bacterial respiratory tract superinfections in the COVID-19 era: a retrospective quantitative analysis of antibiotic consumption and identification of antibiotic prescription drivers. *Intern Emerg Med* [Internet]. 2022;17(1):141–151. doi:10.1007/s11739-021-02790-0. [[PubMed](#)][[Web of Science](#) ®][[Google Scholar](#)]
 81. Bazaid AS, Barnawi H, Qanash H, Alsaif G, Aldarhami A, Gattan H, Alharbi B, Alrashidi A, Al-Soud WA, Moussa S, et al. Bacterial coinfection and antibiotic resistance profiles among hospitalised COVID-19 patients. *Microorgan*. 2022;10(3):495. doi:10.3390/microorganisms10030495. [[PubMed](#)][[Web of Science](#) ®][[Google Scholar](#)]

82. Russell CD, Fairfield CJ, Drake TM, Turtle L, Seaton RA, Wootton DG, Sigfrid L, Harrison EM, Docherty AB, de Silva TI, et al. Co-infections, secondary infections, and antimicrobial use in patients hospitalised with COVID-19 during the first pandemic wave from the ISARIC WHO CCP-UK study: a multicentre, prospective cohort study. *The Lancet Microbe* [Internet]. 2021;2(8):e354–65. doi:10.1016/S2666-5247(21)00090-2. [[PubMed](#)][[Google Scholar](#)]
83. Arcari G, Raponi G, Sacco F, Bibbolino G, Di Lella FM, Alessandri F, Coletti M, Trancassini M, Deales A, Pugliese F, et al. *Klebsiella pneumoniae* infections in COVID-19 patients: a 2-month retrospective analysis in an Italian hospital. *Int J Antimicrob Agents*. 2021;57(1):106245. doi:10.1016/j.ijantimicag.2020.106245. [[PubMed](#)][[Web of Science](#) ®][[Google Scholar](#)]
84. Chong WH, Saha BK, Ramani A, Chopra A. State-of-the-art review of secondary pulmonary infections in patients with COVID-19 pneumonia. *Infection* [Internet]. 2021;49(4):591–605. doi:10.1007/s15010-021-01602-z. [[PubMed](#)][[Web of Science](#) ®][[Google Scholar](#)]
85. Gerver SM, Guy R, Wilson K, Thelwall S, Nsonwu O, Rooney G, Brown CS, Muller-Pebody B, Hope R, Hall V. National surveillance of bacterial and fungal coinfection and secondary infection in COVID-19 patients in England: lessons from the first wave. *Clin Microbiol Infect*. 2021;27(11):1658–1665. doi:10.1016/j.cmi.2021.05.040. [[PubMed](#)][[Web of Science](#) ®][[Google Scholar](#)]
86. Protonotariou E, Mantzana P, Meletis G, Tychala A, Kassomenaki A, Vasilaki O, Kagkalou G, Gkeka I, Archonti M, Kati S, et al. Microbiological characteristics of bacteremias among COVID-19 hospitalized patients in a tertiary referral hospital in Northern Greece during the second epidemic wave. *FEMS Microbes* [Internet]. 2022;2. doi:10.1093/femsmc/xtab021/6448474. [[Google Scholar](#)]
87. Zheng D, Liwinski T, Elinav E. Interaction between microbiota and immunity in health and disease. *Cell Res* [Internet]. 2020;30(6):492–506. doi:10.1038/s41422-020-0332-7. [[PubMed](#)][[Web of Science](#) ®][[Google Scholar](#)]
88. Jang YO, Kim OH, Kim SJ, Lee SH, Yun S, Lim SE, Yoo HJ, Shin Y, Lee SW. High-fiber diets attenuate emphysema development via modulation of gut microbiota and metabolism. *Sci Rep*. 2021;11(1):7008. doi:10.1038/s41598-021-86404-x. [[PubMed](#)][[Web of Science](#) ®][[Google Scholar](#)]
89. Sampson TR, Mazmanian SK. Control of brain development, function, and behavior by the microbiome. *Cell Host & Microbe*. 2015;17(5):565–576. doi:10.1016/j.chom.2015.04.011. [[PubMed](#)][[Web of Science](#) ®][[Google Scholar](#)]
90. Bajinka O, Simbilyabo L, Tan Y, Jabang J, Saleem SA. Lung-brain axis. *Crit Rev Microbiol* [Internet]. 2022;48(3):257–269. doi:10.1080/1040841X.2021.1960483. [[PubMed](#)][[Web of Science](#) ®][[Google Scholar](#)]
91. Hosang L, Canals RC, van der Flier FJ, Hollensteiner J, Daniel R, Flügel A, Odoardi F. The lung microbiome regulates brain autoimmunity. *Nature* [Internet]. 2022;603(7899):138–144. doi:10.1038/s41586-022-04427-4. [[Google Scholar](#)]
92. Monje M, Iwasaki A. The neurobiology of long COVID. *Neuron* [Internet]. 2022;110(21):3484–3496. doi:10.1016/j.neuron.2022.10.006. [[PubMed](#)][[Web of Science](#) ®][[Google Scholar](#)]
93. Taquet M, Geddes JR, Husain M, Luciano S, Harrison PJ. 6-month neurological and psychiatric outcomes in 236 379 survivors of COVID-19: a retrospective cohort study using electronic health records. 57. *The Lancet Psych* [Internet]. 2021;8(5):416–427. doi:10.1016/S2215-0366(21)00084-5. [[PubMed](#)][[Web of Science](#) ®][[Google Scholar](#)]
94. Yang I, Arthur RA, Zhao L, Clark J, Hu Y, Corwin EJ, Lah J. The oral microbiome and inflammation in mild cognitive impairment. *Exp Gerontol*. 2021;147:111273. doi:10.1016/j.exger.2021.111273. [[PubMed](#)][[Web of Science](#) ®][[Google Scholar](#)]

95. Erny D, Hrabě de Angelis AL, Jaitin D, Wieghofer P, Staszewski O, David E, Keren-Shaul H, Muhlrad T, Jakobshagen K, Buch T, et al. Host microbiota constantly control maturation and function of microglia in the CNS. *Nat Neurosci* [Internet]. 2015;18(7):965–977. doi:10.1038/nn.4030. [[PubMed](#)][[Web of Science ®](#)][[Google Scholar](#)]
96. Dang AT, Marsland BJ. Microbes, metabolites, and the gut–lung axis. *Mucosal Immunol* [Internet]. 2019;12(4):843–850. doi:10.1038/s41385-019-0160-6. [[PubMed](#)][[Web of Science ®](#)][[Google Scholar](#)]
97. Doifode T, Giridharan VV, Generoso JS, Bhatti G, Collodel A, Schulz PE, Forlenza OV, Barichello T. 61. The impact of the microbiota-gut-brain axis on Alzheimer’s disease pathophysiology. *Pharmacol Res*. 2021;164:105314. doi:10.1016/j.phrs.2020.105314. [[PubMed](#)][[Web of Science ®](#)][[Google Scholar](#)]
98. Saia RS, Giusti H, Luis-Silva F, Pedroso K, Auxiliadora-Martins M, Morejón KML, Degiovani AM, Cadelca MR, Basile-Filho A. Clinical investigation of intestinal fatty acid-binding protein (I-FABP) as a biomarker of SARS-CoV-2 infection. *Int J Infect Dis* [Internet]. 2021;113:82–86. doi:10.1016/j.ijid.2021.09.051. [[PubMed](#)][[Web of Science ®](#)][[Google Scholar](#)]
99. Mańkowska-Wierzbicka D, Zuraszek J, Wierzbicka A, Gabryel M, Mahadea D, Baturo A, Zakerska-Banaszak O, Slomski R, Skrzypczak-Zielinska M, Dobrowolska A. Alterations in gut microbiota composition in patients with COVID-19: a pilot study of whole hypervariable 16S rRNA gene sequencing. *Biomed*. 2023;11(2):11. doi:10.3390/biomedicines11020367.[[Google Scholar](#)]
100. Al Bataineh MT, Henschel A, Mousa M, Daou M, Waasia F, Kannout H, Khalili M, Kayasseh MA, Alkhajeh A, Uddin M. Gut microbiota interplay with COVID-19 reveals links to host lipid metabolism among middle eastern populations. *Front Microbiol*. 2021;12:12. doi:10.3389/fmicb.2021.761067. [[Web of Science ®](#)][[Google Scholar](#)]
101. Jang SE, Lim SM, Jeong JJ, Jang HM, Lee HJ, Han MJ, Kim DH. Gastrointestinal inflammation by gut microbiota disturbance induces memory impairment in mice. *Mucosal Immunol*. 2018;11(2):369–379. doi:10.1038/mi.2017.49. [[PubMed](#)][[Web of Science ®](#)][[Google Scholar](#)]
102. Kim N, Jeon SH, Ju IG, Gee MS, Do J, Oh MS, Lee JK. Transplantation of gut microbiota derived from alzheimer’s disease mouse model impairs memory function and neurogenesis in C57BL/6 mice. *Brain Behav Immun* [Internet]. 2021;98:357–365. doi:10.1016/j.bbi.2021.09.002. [[PubMed](#)][[Web of Science ®](#)][[Google Scholar](#)]
103. Vieira AT, Galvão I, Amaral FA, Teixeira MM, Nicoli JR, Martins FS. Oral treatment with bifidobacterium longum 5 1A reduced inflammation in a murine experimental model of gout. *Benef Microbes* [Internet]. 2015;6(6):799–806. doi:10.3920/BM2015.0015.[[PubMed](#)][[Web of Science ®](#)][[Google Scholar](#)]
104. Alharbi KS, Singh Y, Hassan Almalki W, Rawat S, Afzal O, Alfawaz Altamimi AS, Kazmi I, Al-Abbasi FA, Alzarea SI, Singh SK, et al. Gut microbiota disruption in COVID-19 or post-COVID illness association with severity biomarkers: a possible role of pre/pro-biotics in manipulating microflora. *Chem Biol Interact*. 2022;358:109898. doi:10.1016/j.cbi.2022.109898. [[PubMed](#)][[Web of Science ®](#)][[Google Scholar](#)]
105. Mukhopadhyay I, Segal JP, Carding SR, Hart AL, Hold GL. The gut virome: the “missing link” between gut bacteria and host immunity? *Therap Adv Gastroenterol*. 2019;12:1756284819836620. doi:10.1177/1756284819836620. [[Web of Science ®](#)][[Google Scholar](#)]
106. Yuan L, Hensley C, Mahsoub HM, Ramesh AK, Zhou P. Microbiota in viral infection and disease in humans and farm animals. *Prog Mol Biol Transl Sci*. 2020;171:15–60. doi:10.1016/bs.pmbts.2020.04.005. [[PubMed](#)][[Web of Science ®](#)][[Google Scholar](#)]
107. Lu ZH, Zhou HW, Wu WK, Fu T, Yan M, He Z, Sun SW, Ji ZH, Shao Z. Alterations in the composition of intestinal DNA virome in patients with COVID-19 [Internet]. *Front Cell*

- Infect Microbiol. 2021;11:11. doi:10.3389/fcimb.2021.790422. [[Web of Science ®](#)][[Google Scholar](#)]
- 108.71. Natarajan A, Zlitni S, Brooks EF, Vance SE, Dahlen A, Hedlin H, Park RM, Han A, Schmidtke DT, Verma R, et al. Gastrointestinal symptoms and fecal shedding of SARS-CoV-2 RNA suggest prolonged gastrointestinal infection. *Med* [Internet]. 2022;3(6):371–387.e9. doi:10.1016/j.medj.2022.04.001. [[Google Scholar](#)]
- 109.72. Chen, Y., Gu, S., Chen, Y., Lu, H., Shi, D., Guo, J., et al. (2022). Six-month follow-up of gut microbiota richness in patients with COVID-19. *Gut*. 71, 222–225. doi: 10.1136/gutjnl-2021-324090 [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Crossref Full Text](#) | [Google Scholar](#)